

THERMOPLASTIC BONDING TO METALS VIA INJECTION MOLDING FOR MACRO-COMPOSITE MANUFACTURE

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SUMMARY: In this work, we explore a new method of in-situ joining of polymers to metals in injection molding to allow direct bonding between thermoplastic and metal parts. Such a method can integrate several down-stream steps in product manufacture, allow optimal design of products and joints, avoid adhesive application, assembly, and associated difficulties. A variety of process parameters and their effects upon the interface tensile strengths were examined. A full factorial experiment was conducted involving four of the critical process parameters identified. The effects upon tensile strength at break of the following process parameters were studied: 1) adherend surface temperature, 2) screw linear velocity, 3) bond-line thickness, and 4) pack and hold pressure. The fracture surfaces and the thermoplastic-metal interfaces were analyzed. The bonds fabricated with higher adherend surface temperatures had increased mean tensile strength and less adhesive failure. This increase in mean bond tensile strength and less adhesive failure was due to increased polymer penetration of the adherend surface roughness, at the μm level, as shown in the analysis of the polymer-metal interface.

KEYWORDS: bonding, thermoplastic, injection molding, tensile, fracture, polycarbonate, steel

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic adhesive bonding via injection molding is shown to be a cost effective method to create net shape polymer-metal macro-composites with interfaces of appreciable tensile strength. Traditionally, complex parts consisting of net shape plastic parts and metallic substrates are joined using thermoset adhesives or insert molding with special features. Thermoset adhesives use a separate assembly process and need time to cure. Joining in-situ in injection molding offers reduced times and steps to manufacture, is insensitive to tolerances required in assembly, and creates a stable interface. In this study, a thermoplastic was injection molded onto a grit blasted metal substrate to create tensile butt joints.

MOTIVATION

The primary objective of this research is to develop in-situ processes to join thermoplastics to metals in an injection molding process. In our earlier studies a hot-melt process was used as the model environment [1-3]. The surface preparation, contact pressure during consolidation,

heating and cooling rates, hold times at melt and recrystallization temperature, effect of bond line thickness and uniformity, and anodization to increase durability were included in the process development [4]. In a parallel study, the residual stresses between both amorphous and semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymers and metals are modeled and validated [5].

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The objective of the experiments was to study the effects of injection molding process parameters upon the tensile strength of a butt joint. A butt joint eliminated the contribution of shrinkage stresses to bond strength which would occur in insert molded joints. The tensile test specimen consisted of 2 cylindrical rods (19.05 mm diameter) of 1018 low carbon steel. The bonding surfaces of the steel were grit blasted with 60 grit aluminum oxide. The bonding surfaces were scrubbed with a nylon brush and soaked in isopropyl alcohol to remove loose alumina grit. The steel inserts were then soaked in a bath of isopropyl alcohol and ultrasonically cleaned for 30 minutes. Reverse osmosis (RO) water was not used for cleaning because the steel inserts began to rust when soaked.

Figure 1: Mold Assembly Drawing

A special mold was designed to create tensile butt joint specimens of variable thickness (See Figure 1). The thickness of polymer between the two steel inserts was controlled with the use of shims of variable length. Additionally, a mold insert was designed to allow for variable gate dimensions. The injection molding was carried out on a 55 ton Cincinnati Milacron model VST 55 injection molding machine with a 32 mm diameter screw.

The limits of the ranges of several process parameters were explored in preliminary experiments. With a polymer cavity thickness of 0.3 mm, the mold filling was not consistent for every cycle due to variation in process parameters beyond the control of the operator. A polymer thickness of 0.5mm was used as a minimum since the resulting mold filling was consistent from cycle to cycle. Steel inserts without preheating were also used for creating

butt joints, however, the bond broke upon ejection from the mold. Several process parameters, such as length of ultrasonic cleaning time of the steel inserts were eliminated when it was determined that the parameter in question had no significant effect upon the bond tensile strength. As a result of these preliminary experiments, the following four process parameters were selected for a full factorial study: 1) adherend surface temperature, 2) injection screw linear velocity, 3) polymer thickness, and 4) pack and hold pressure.

Various methods of heating the rods in-situ were also investigated such as heating the adherend surface with a nitrogen hot gas torch. The hot gas torch effectively heated the adherend surface without heating the insert or mold below the surface. However, as soon as the torch was removed, the adherend surface rapidly cooled below the glass transition temperature resulting in very weak or no bonding. Therefore, the steel bars were heated in an oven prior to insertion into the mold. The oven temperature was set to either 316°C or 399°C to achieve the variations in the adherend surface temperatures. The steel samples remained in the oven for a period of 30 minutes to allow the entire insert to achieve thermal equilibrium with the oven.

After preheating, the steel rods were then inserted into the mold held at a constant temperature of 121°C. The adherend surface temperature was recorded using a Heimann model KT 15.82 infrared (IR) thermometer. Due to space constraints, the IR thermometer had to be placed at angle of approximately 40° below the horizontal plane. Due to this angle and the distance of the IR thermometer from the adherend surface, the actual area from which the IR thermometer collected data was ellipsoidal in shape with a major axis of 17mm and a minor axis of 13mm. The adherend surface temperature versus time was recorded using Labview data recording software. Mold filling occurred five seconds after the mold began to close, however the last adherend surface temperature data point was recorded just before mold closure began. Therefore, a decaying exponential curve fit was applied to the data and extrapolated for 5 seconds to estimate the adherend surface temperature at the time of mold filling. The molding machine filled the cavity between the two steel bars with GE Lexan polycarbonate in approximately 0.33 seconds.

After removal of the test specimens from the mold, the parts were allowed to cool to room temperature. The butt joint tensile specimens were then tested on a QTEST-VII testing machine with a constant crosshead speed of 5.08 mm per minute.

To study the bond interface region, several specimens were created using 6061-T6 aluminum alloy as opposed to 1018 steel. The aluminum adherends were grit blasted similar to the steel. Tensile bars were created using three different adherend preheating methods: high heat, low heat, and no heat. For the high heat and low heat, the oven was set to the same temperature as for the steel (i.e., 399°C and 316°C respectively). For all of the aluminum tests, an injection velocity of 10.668 cm/sec, bond thickness of 0.5 mm, and pack and hold pressure of 190 MPa were used. All other injection molding parameters remained the same. The bulk of the aluminum was removed from the bond area using a band saw, leaving approximately 2 mm of aluminum on both sides of the polycarbonate. During cutting on the band saw, the bond area was not heated significantly. The remaining aluminum was removed from the polycarbonate by soaking the pieces in a 15% solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) for approximately 24 hours. After 24 hours, the aluminum had completely dissolved away, exposing the polycarbonate bond interfacial surface. No visible deterioration of the polycarbonate due to the soak in the NaOH occurred. For the non-preheated aluminum, the polycarbonate did not bond to the aluminum. The polycarbonate discs were ultrasonically cleaned in isopropyl

alcohol for 10 minutes. The discs were then sputter coated with a thin layer (10-20nm) of gold/palladium (Au/Pd). The Au/Pd layer facilitates viewing the polycarbonate in the scanning electron microscope (SEM) by providing a conductive surface layer which prevents charging of the polymer surface. The polycarbonate bond interfacial surface was viewed on a JEOL 35CT SEM at an accelerating voltage of 15kV.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Statistical Analysis

The tensile test data was statistically analyzed using the SAS statistical analysis software. A plot of the residuals versus normal quantiles yields a nearly linear relationship which is indicative of normally distributed data. The program computed the mean strength values for each parameter level setting (See Table 1).

Table 1: Statistical Analysis of Results

Parameter	Level Setting		Mean Bond Tensile Strength (MPa)	Statistical Confidence	Statistically Significant
Mean Adherend Surface Temperature (°C)	Hi	204	30.8	0.9999	YES
	Low	170	20.4		
Screw Linear Velocity (cm/sec)	Hi	10.668	26.4	0.3550	NO
	Low	5.080	25.3		
Polymer Thickness (mm)	Hi	1.0	23.9	0.6550	NO
	Low	0.5	27.6		
Pack and Hold Pressure (MPa)	Hi	190	24.8	0.9150	NO
	Low	129	26.9		

A Student-Newman-Keuls test was performed to analyze the statistical significance of the parameters' effects upon the mean bond tensile strength. The adherend surface temperature had the most significant effect upon the mean bond tensile strength. Changes in the injection screw linear velocity, polymer thickness, and pack and hold pressure did not have a significant effect upon the mean bond tensile strength.

The interaction among adherend surface temperature, screw linear velocity, and polymer cavity thickness proved to be the only interaction of significance (0.9996 statistical confidence). In Figure 2 for a constant pack and hold pressure of 190 MPa, the bond tensile strength for the optimum level settings for these three parameters is compared to the bond strength for the opposite level settings.

For the range of process parameters considered, the bond tensile strength is directly proportional to adherend surface temperature and screw linear velocity, and inversely proportional to polymer thickness. The bond strength is relatively insensitive to pack and hold pressures.

In the population of bonds created with a low injection screw linear velocity, bonds of negligible strength (< 5 MPa) occurred with a much higher frequency than in the population of bonds created with a higher injection screw linear velocity. This observation provides another reason to avoid low screw linear velocities.

Figure 2: Comparison of Bond Strengths for Interaction of Adherend Surface Temperature, Screw Linear Velocity, and Polymer Thickness at Constant Pack and Hold Pressure of 190MPa

Fracture Surface Analysis

Observation of the fracture surfaces reveals that adhesive failure occurred on all of the specimens to varying degrees. A general trend was that the higher bond tensile strength pairs showed a lower area of adhesive failure. Comparing Figures 3a-b and 4a-b, it was observed that the failure surfaces for those bonds created with a low adherend surface temperature reveal more adhesive failure than bonds created with a higher adherend surface temperature.

Figures 3a-b: Fracture Surface Pair from Bond Created with Low Adherend Surface Temperature

Figures 4a-b: Fracture Surface Pair from Bond Created with High Adherend Surface Temperature

Additionally, for some of the higher strength bonds, the adhesive failure tended to occur near the gate area (See Figures 5a-b).

Figures 5a-b: Fracture Surface Pair from Bond Created with High Adhesive Surface Temperature Showing Adhesive Failure Near Gate

Bond Interface Microanalysis

Surface profilometry measurements were taken of the grit blasted aluminum surface and the three polycarbonate surfaces (no preheat, low preheating, and high preheating). The radius of the profilometer stylus tip was $5\mu\text{m}$. The R_a values were approximately $3\mu\text{m}$ for all four surfaces.

Observing the polycarbonate surfaces in an SEM at 200X magnification revealed no apparent differences among the surfaces of grit blasted aluminum, and the polycarbonate surfaces for the three preheating conditions. However, at 4800X magnification the differences among the three preheating conditions are apparent. For the polycarbonate injection molded over the non-preheated aluminum surface, the polycarbonate is predominantly smooth. The few ridges that were observed exhibit smooth edges (See Figures 6a-b).

Figures 6a-b: SEM of Polycarbonate Surface with No Aluminum Preheating

SEM micrographs of the polycarbonate bonded to the aluminum preheated in the oven at 316°C show considerably more roughness than the unheated specimens (See Figures 7a-b). Additionally, the edges of the ridges exhibit more rough features.

Figures 7a-b: SEM of Polycarbonate Surface with Low Preheating

SEM micrographs of the polycarbonate bonded to the aluminum preheated in the oven at 399°C show similar medium (1-5µm) and large scale (>5µm) roughness (See Figures 8a-b). Additionally, the high heat specimens exhibit small scale (<1µm) surface pits.

Figures 8a-b: SEM of Polycarbonate Surface with High Preheating

An SEM micrograph of the grit blasted aluminum surface is shown for comparison (See Figure 12). Notice the small scale (<1 μ m) surface protrusions which are the cause for the pits on the polycarbonate bonded with high preheating of the aluminum.

Figure 9: SEM of Aluminum Surface

While the large scale (>5 μ m) roughness of all four surfaces is approximately equivalent (See the profilometry results of the previous page), the small (<1 μ m) and medium scale (1-5 μ m) roughness differ significantly (as shown in Figures 6 through 9).

Bond Strength Variance Analysis

The variation in bond tensile strength is due to variations in several process parameters including adherend surface temperature and hydraulic transfer pressure. The mean adherend surface temperature of 204°C and a standard deviation of 14°C result in bonds with a strength of 30.8 MPa. The mean adherend surface temperature of 170°C and a standard deviation of 12 °C result in bonds with a mean bond strength of 20.4 MPa. If we assume, from the results of the full factorial study, that an increase in adherend surface temperature of 34°C (204°C - 170°C) results in an increase in bond strength of 10.4 MPa, then the variations in adherend surface temperature of 14°C and 12°C would contribute 4.3 MPa and 3.7 MPa to the variation in the mean bond tensile strength respectively.

The deviation in the bond tensile strength data is larger than the deviation attributed to variation in adherend surface temperature, suggesting that other factors or interactions are affecting the bond strength. Included among these noise factors is the hydraulic transfer pressure (the pressure at the screw tip when screw reaches the transfer position), which varied as much as 35 MPa from a nominal value of 138 MPa in a particular test group.

Viscosity Effects on Bond Strength

The increase in mean bond tensile strength with increased adherend surface temperature is due to increased penetration of surface roughness. Polymer viscosity is primarily a function of temperature and shear rate. For polycarbonate, the apparent viscosity is relatively insensitive to the shear rate [6]. The polymer viscosity is related to the polymer temperature by Equation 1.

$$\eta = A e^{E/RT} \quad (1)$$

where η is a defined shear viscosity, E is a viscous energy of activation for the polymer, R is the gas constant, T is absolute temperature, and A is a pre-exponential coefficient [6]. It was assumed that the polymer in contact with the adherend surface was at the same temperature as the adherend surface. For the high adherend surface temperature of 204°C, the melt viscosity of polycarbonate is 250,000 poise (g/cm-sec) at a shear rate of 10 radians per second [7]. For the low adherend temperature of 170°C, the melt viscosity for polycarbonate is over 1,500,000 poise (g/cm-sec) at a shear rate of 10 radians per second [7]. The significantly lower polymer viscosity at the higher adherend surface temperature allows the polycarbonate to penetrate the adherend surface micro-roughness to a greater degree. The scanning electron micrographs (Figures 6-8) confirm the fact that a greater amount of penetration of the small scale surface micro roughness (<1 μ m) is present in the bonds prepared with the higher adherend surface temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

A full factorial study of 1) adherend surface temperature, 2) screw linear velocity, 3) bond-line thickness, and 4) pack and hold pressure showed that adherend surface temperature was the most significant factor. The interaction among adherend surface temperature, screw linear velocity, and polymer cavity thickness proved to be the only interaction of significance. An increase in mean adherend surface temperature from 170°C to 204°C improved the bond strength from 20.4 MPa to 30.8 MPa on average. The increase in mean adherend surface temperature is due to increased polymer penetration of the adherend surface small scale (<1 μ m) roughness.

This study demonstrated in-situ joining of thermoplastics to metal in an injection molding process. Injection molding on a grit blasted surface proves to be a cost effective and eco-friendly method to manufacture macro-composites with polymer-metal interfaces of significant tensile strength.

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